

Research Article

Assessment of the Physicochemical and Biological Characteristics of Water in Hand Dug Wells within Jos Metropolis, Plateau State, Nigeria

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Abstract

Jos Metropolis is struggling to cope with serious water shortage and the inadequacy of the existing water infrastructure. There has been no sufficient supply of pipe borne water to Jos Metropolis. Majority of people living within the environment depend on water from hand dug wells for their water needs. Physical, chemical and bacteriological evaluation of twenty one hand dug well water employing standard method was carried out with a view to characterize and ascertain their portability. The physical analysis revealed that pH ranged from 6.00 – 7.60 (av. 6.66) indicating almost neutral water. Electrical Conductivity (EC) of 708.00 – 989.00 (av.894.33) $\mu\text{S/cm}$ and TH of 18.00 – 570.00 mg/L, revealed soft water with low dissolved solid. Result of the chemical analysis showed that Ca^{2+} ranged from 58.00 – 91.00 (av.73.90) mg/L, Mg^{2+} from 0.00 – 3.02 (av. 0.18) mg/L, Na^+ from 90.00 – 150.00 (av.118.7) mg/L and K^+ from 6.00 – 17.00 (av. 9.14) mg/L. This study revealed that the well water samples analyzed in the study area indicated that most of the parameters are within the approved WHO standards for drinking water except for the samples from wells No: 20, 4, 11, and 14 (Mungel Jos South,) (Naraguta B, Yan shanu, Yan doya all in Jos North) have Turbidity concentration of 10.34NTU, 18.3NTU and Total Coliform of 80/100ml, 69/100ml respectively against the WHO standard guideline values of Turbidity of 5NTU and Total Coliform of 0-10/100ml. The research indicated that the well water is soft, low mineralized and potable with the exception of few.

Keywords: Bacteriological, Characteristics, Hand Dug Well, Jos Metropolis, Water Quality Parameters, Physicochemical.

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Introduction

Water is one of the most important and most precious natural resources. It is essential in the life of all living organisms from the simplest plant and microorganisms to the most complex living system known as human body. Water is life, adequate supply of water is central to life and civilization of the five basic human needs namely air, water, food, light, and heat, water is common factor to other four. It is therefore not an understatement to say water is life, because it forms an appreciable proportion of all living things including man. Water is continually reprocessed and delivers to the land by hydrological cycle in its liquid state for man's utilization. This is due to the fact that during dry season, water supply from various sources hardly meet the water need of the urban populace (Osieyo, 2016). Access to safe drinking water is key to sustainable development and essential to food production, quality health and poverty reduction. Safe drinking water is essential to life and a satisfactory safe supply must be made available to consumers. High population growth has accelerated water demand tremendously within the study area cum the demand for freshwater meant for domestic use and processing of food for consumption purpose (Antipas *et al*, 2015).

The hand dug well water is used by those living around the metropolis vicinity for washing, cooking, laboratory work and bathing.

Water is vital for the sustenance of life and the economic development of a country. In Nigeria, the Government has put in place different programmes aimed at improving and stabilizing the water supply condition of its populace, but Nigeria is still facing serious water challenges due to change in climate, high demand for drinking water, urban expansion and population explosion (Ezeabasili *et al.*, 2014).

Water is a carrier of undesirable physical, chemical and bacteriological matters that constitute contaminants and to higher degrees pollutants (Haylay *et al.*, 2018). The sanitary certainty of water has to be regularly monitored, analyzed and evaluated to check the influx of unwanted matters and to ensure the safety of the consumers. Quality drinking water is essential for life (Ince and Bashir, 2010). Water scarcity is one important challenge that faces communities that hitherto lack pipe borne water or surface water supply. Water is an everyday commodity need of man and all efforts should be made to make it available in sufficient quantity and quality.

According to the Nigerian National Water Policy (2006), the nation's water sources are under serious threat from inadequate catchment management and widespread

pollution, including the indiscriminate disposal of hazardous substances. There is limited groundwater availability in the areas of the country underlain by crystalline rocks (Yakubu *et al.*, 2017). In the more productive sedimentary areas, groundwater exploitation is heavy and uncontrolled. In addition to above challenges, poor watershed management, deteriorating water quality, drought and desertification are inexorably increasing water scarcity. Scarcity threatens urban and rural developments with rapidly rising water supply costs, reduced reliability of water supplies, prolonged droughts, flood and erosion and increasing costs of irrigated food production. Water-related diseases are a major cause of morbidity and mortality, with malaria, diarrhea, schistosomiasis, onchocerciasis and guinea worm all posing serious threats to public health (Ukpong and Abaraogu, 2014). Thus this study aimed at determining the physico-chemical characteristics of hand dug wells around Jos metropolis with a view to characterize the water and ascertain its suitability for domestic purposes.

STUDY AREA

Jos Metropolis is located in the middle belt zone of Nigeria. It lies between Latitudes N09°48'.396" to N 09°57'.194" and Longitudes E 008° 50'.100" to E 008°54'.547" and at an average elevation of 1238m above sea level. It has a population of 1,007,489 people (using geometric growth rate method with growth rate of 2.7% with 2006 Census). Jos metropolis has a Land area of about 9,400km². The area experiences an average monthly temperature of 21⁰C to 25⁰C from November to late January. Jos Plateau share a common boundary with Bauchi State in the north. The Metropolis cuts across two Local Government Areas such as Jos North and Jos South as shown in Figure 1. The Metropolis covers part of Jos north and Jos south. It is the state capital and the heart of the City. Most commercial, social and educational activities take place in this area. The metropolis shares a common boundary with Bauchi State in the north, Jos east LGA in the east, Basa LGA in the west and Barkin Ladi LGA in the south as shown on Figure 1

Figure 1. Map of the study locations in Jos Metropolis

Materials and Methods

Two major steps were involved in the collection of hand-dug well data for this research (Field operation and Laboratory analysis). The field operations were conducted using etrex GARMIN GPS for coordinates (Latitudes, Longitudes and Elevations readings), while Measuring tape, rope and well-drawers were used to measure the Depth, Diameter, Static water level, thickness and depth of the Head walls of the selected wells and distance from contaminants (septic tank/ soak way, street gutter, refuse dump, mining ponds). Twenty-One (21) well water samples were collected into polyethylene bottles that have been thoroughly washed. All samples were refrigerated at a temperature of -4°C before being transported to the Plateau State Water Board Laboratory at Dogon Karfe in Jos North LGA of Plateau State, Nigeria for analysis. Chemical, Physical, and Bacteriological analysis of samples were conducted using the water quality analysis methods indicated on Table 1 and the results were appraised in accordance with drinking water quality standards recommended by the World Health Organization WHO (2004).

Sample collection

A total of 21 water wells were randomly selected, 13 from Jos North LGA and 8 from Jos South LGA where hand dug wells water are extensively used for drinking and other Domestic purposes. The water samples were collected using sterile plastic bottles, following the appropriate procedures. Parameters such as total coliform, faecal coliform, pH, conductivity, turbidity, TDS, total hardness, fluoride, sulphate, nitrite and nitrate were analysed from the samples using standard methods referred to previously and the spectrophotometer. Sensitive parameters such as temperature and pH were measured immediately after collection of the well water samples. The Crison Basic 20 pH meter and a mercury thermometer was used for pH and temperature measurements, respectively.

Chemical analysis

A photometric method was used for the determination of NO_3^- , NO_2^- and SO_4^{2-} as these are nutrients related to pollutants. Analytical water test tablets prescribed for Palintest Photometer 5000 (Wagtech, Thatcham, Berkshire, UK) series were used. Each sample was analysed for NO_3^- , NO_2^- and SO_4^{2-} using procedures outlined in the Palintest Photometer Method (Palintest, US) for the examination of drinking water and wastewater. Other analyses such as the determination of total hardness and F- were done by complexometric titration using Ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid (EDTA). The determination of concentrations was completed using Argentometric titration. Total

dissolved solids and electrical conductivity were determined by a means of a multifunctional WTW cond. 730 series, conductivity meter.

Microbial analysis

Samples for bacteriological analyses were kept in screw-capped bottles that have been sterilized in an autoclave for 15 min at 121°C. Samples were then transferred to the laboratory where they were stored in the refrigerator for microbial analyses. Standard methods for the determination of total and faecal coliforms (National Water Policy (2006) were employed.

Results and Discussion

Certain specific parameters were analyzed according to the physico-chemical and bacteriological standards established by the WHO for drinking water quality. The results obtain during the analysis of the physicochemical and bacteriological parameters of hand dug wells water samples were presented in Tables 1 and 2.

pH

The pH is a measure of hydrogen ion concentration in water. According to WHO, drinking water with a pH between 6.5 to 8.5 are generally considered satisfactory. In this study, the values of pH in Tables 1 and 2 ranged from 6.0 to 7.60 for hand dug well water. This result indicated the neutral and alkaline nature of the hand dug well water. From the Table 1, the highest and the lowest pH were well no. 16 and 14 (Zarmaganda in Jos South and Gangare in Jos North). All these values were within the accepted limits. If the pH value is below 6. Alkaline waters are less corrosive; water with Ph above 8.5 may tend to have a bitter or soda-like taste. In this study, the concentration of hydrogen ion (pH) of hand-dug wells range between 6.0 and 7.6. All the water samples analyzed have concentration within the safe limit of 6.5 to 8.5 standard set by the WHO. Thus indicated that the measured pH values of the drinking water samples were within permissible values of WHO; which will not cause any harmful effect to the consumers in terms of pH. pH is the most important parameter that serves as an index for pollution and also measures the hydrogen ion concentration (H⁺) and negative hydroxide ion (OH⁻) in water. Although pH usually has no direct impact on consumers, it is one of the most important operational water quality parameters. Low pH water is likely to be corrosive. Alkalinity and calcium management also contribute to the stability of water and control its aggressiveness to pipes and appliances.

Turbidity

Turbidity values varied from 1.24 to 18.30 NTU for hand dug well water analyzed, some of the values analyzed were very low below the WHO 5 NTU limits, while some were above the limits. Turbidity may be defined as the measure of clarity of water, high turbidity may indicate the presence of disease causing organisms such as bacteria, viruses and parasite that causes symptoms like nausea, cramps, diarrhea and headaches. It is also caused by the presence of suspended insoluble materials such as clay and silt particles, discharges of sewage or industrial wastes, or the presence of large numbers of micro-organisms mainly occurring in surface water, which makes them objectionable for almost all uses. Excessive turbidity protects microorganisms from effects of disinfectants and stimulates the growth of bacteria in water.

Total Dissolved Solids (TDS)

TDS can be taken as an indicator for the general water quality because it directly affects the aesthetic value of the water by increasing turbidity. High concentration of TDS limits the suitability of water as a drinking source and irrigation supply. The acceptable range of TDS is 1500 mg/L In the present study, the range of TDS of analyzed hand dug well water samples varied between 819 and 998. All the water samples analyzed have TDS concentration within the safe limit of 1500mg/l standard set by the WHO. Thus indicated that the measured TDS values of the drinking water samples were within permissible values of WHO; which will not cause any harmful effect to the consumers in terms of TDS.

Chemical parameter

Electrical Conductivity (EC)

The ability of a solution to conduct an electrical current is governed by the migration of solutions and is depending on the nature and numbers of the ionic species in that solution. This property is called electrical conductivity. It is a useful tool to assess the purity of water. The permissible limit for electrical conductivity (EC) is 1,000 μScm^{-1} . The EC of the collected samples ranged from 708 μScm^{-1} to 989 μScm^{-1} . This showed that the EC values of all water samples were within the permissible limits. Therefore the water is potable and safe to consume in terms of EC.

Chloride

The chlorides in water are known to come from rainwater. The accepted values are between 200 and 600 mg/L. In this study, the values of Chloride obtained in well water ranges between 79 and 150 were mg/L, the chloride levels recorded from all the samples were within the drinking water quality (250 mg/L) by the WHO acceptable

limit. These water samples were thus low in chlorides and thus of good quality with respect to chlorides.

Total Hardness (TH)

In groundwater, hardness is mainly contributed by bicarbonates, carbonates, sulphates and chlorides of calcium and magnesium. So the principal hardness causing ions are calcium and magnesium. The acceptable limit of total hardness is 500mg/L. The hardness of analyzed samples from hand-dug wells ranged between 32mg/L to 570mg/L, private boreholes ranged between 53mg/L to 61mg/L and total hardness of public water is 53mg/L. The highest value of 570mg/L total hardness was observed at Sarki Street (W3) in Jos North sample site which classified water as very hard. On the basis of this classification, it was observed that no water samples are soft but all the measured values were within the acceptable limit values of WHO 500mg/L with the exception of Sarki Street in Ibrahim Katsin ward of Jos North which indicated that it is not acceptable for consumption.

Nitrates

The nitrates in water result from pollution by urines and agricultural entrants. The value recommended by WHO is between 40 - 50 mg/L. The elevated nitrate contents cause the disease known as "Blue-baby". In this study, Nitrate values recorded from hand dug well ranges between 15 mg/L to 25 mg/L indicating that the water is safe for consumption in terms of nitrate.

Microbiological Parameters

Levels of total coliform recorded from most of the wells in this study exceeded WHO guideline value in drinking water which is nil. However, faecal coliform count in the wells showed an increasing trend as the period of this research was in the wet season which may be due to runoff from polluted sources such as septic tanks located nearby or from waste dumps as short distances from pollution sources indicated on the Table 2. The distances ranged from 0.4m to 7.6m.

The Total Coliform values obtained from hand dug well samples ranges between 6/100ml to 80/100ml with an average of 36/100ml indicating that hand dug wells had high contend of Total Coliform which may require treatment before consumption.

Table 1: Physico -chemical and bacteriological parameters of selected hand dug wells in the study area

Code	PH	Total dissolved	Turbidity (NTU)	Total Hardness	MS (Mg/L)	Ca (Mg/L)	CL (Mg/L)	Fe (Mg/L)	K (Mg/L)	E. Conductivity (µs/cm)	Mn (mg/L)	So ₄ (Mg/L)	Na (Mg/L)	NO ₃ (mg/l)	Total Coliform (MPN/100ml)
Well 1	7.2	902	9.2	47	0.002	59	112	0.02	11	902	0.02	89	123	23	34
Well 2	7.4	940	5.7	80	0.001	68	120	0.01	7	940	0.01	89	120	19	6
Well 3	6.2	905	8.89	570	0.003	70	150	0.02	9	905	0.02	100	99	20	26
Well 4	7.2	899	18.3	83	0.002	69	160	0.02	10	899	0.01	140	100	18	45
Well 5	6.2	918	8.8	98	0.02	91	100	0.01	8	918	0.01	145	122	22	50
Well 6	7	930	12.8	40	0.01	88	95	0.03	6	930	0.01	150	120	16	54
Well 7	7	943	8.93	85	0.02	67	98	0.02	11	943	0.02	99	98	15	7
Well 8	6.5	935	6.02	72	0.1	73	105	0.03	6	935	0.01	105	150	20	28
well 9	6	900	2.31	100	0.03	78	85	0.01	8	900	0.02	109	144	22	39
Well10	6.8	905	6.3	32	0.2	58	88	0.02	6	905	0.02	124	126	18	40
Well 11	6.4	895	1.24	210	0.003	77	140	0.03	10	885	0.02	130	110	20	80
Well 12	6.2	900	4.18	228	0.01	88	128	0.1	17	708	0.01	121	122	25	21
Well 13	6.8	819	3.75	418	0.003	76	180	0.02	8	805	0.01	122	106	19	45
Well 14	6	998	5.32	56	0.01	69	167	0.01	9	898	0.02	109	90	15	69
Well 15	6.4	913	7.04	18	0.02	59	99	0.02	6	815	0.01	101	99	16	40
Well 16	7.6	910	14	80	0.01	69	98	0.02	8	902	0.03	105	120	22	36
Well 17	7.2	896	1.96	42	0.02	74	89	0.03	13	980	0.02	97	130	17	23
Well 18	6.4	915	1.64	40	0.1	78	104	0.02	16	819	0.01	148	140	19	30
Well 19	6.4	889	2.22	200	3.02	88	79	0.02	6	814	0.02	122	150	18	18
Well 20	6.5	914	10.34	180	0.04	65	86	0.03	9	989	0.01	120	126	24	35
Well 21	6.4	902	2.3	220	0.2	88	88	0.04	8	989	0.03	98	98	18	29

Table 2: Statistical presentation of the Parameters

PARAMETERS	UNIT	MINIMUM	MAXIMUM	MEAN	STANDARD DEVIATION	WHO GUIDELINE
pH	-	6.00	7.60	6.66	0.47	6.5-8.5
TOTAL DISOLVED SOLID	mg/L	819.00	998.00	910.36	32.01	1500
TURBIDITY	mg/L	1.24	1830	6.75	4.55	5
TOTAL HARDNESS	mg/L	18.00	570.00	138.05	137.80	500
Mg	mg/L	0.00	3.02	0.18	0.65	150
Ca	mg/L	58.00	91.00	73.90	10.20	
Cl	mg/L	79.00	180.00	112.90	29.30	250
Fe	mg/L	0.01	0.10	0.03	0,02	0.3
K	mg/L	6.00	17.00	9.14	3.10	
Conductivity	μScm^{-1}	708.00	989.00	894.33	68.90	1000
Mn	mg/L	0.01	0.03	0.02	0.00	0.2
SO ₂	mg/L	89.00	150.00	115.38	18.99	100
Na	mg/L	90.00	150.00	118.71	17.86	200
NO ₃	mg/L	15.00	25.00	19.33	2.85	50
Total Coliform	MPN	6.00	80.00	35.95	17.97	0-10

Figure 2: Features of Selected Hand dug wells in Jos Metropolis

Location	Turbidity (NTU)	Turbidity (NTU) WHO
Jos North Tafawa Balewa (W1)	9.2	5
Jos North Ali Kazaure (W2)	5.7	5
Jos North Ibrahim Katsina (W3)	8.89	5
Jos North Naraguta B (W4)	18.3	5
Jos North Jenta Adamu (W5)	8.8	5
Jos North Ziks Avenue (W6)	12.8	5
Jos North Tudun Wada (W7)	8.93	5
Jos North Apata (W8)	6.02	5
Jos North Jos Jarawa (W9)	2.31	5
Jos North Cole Street (W10)	6.3	5
Jos North Naraguta A (W11)	1.24	5
Jos North Dodo street (W12)	4.18	5
Jos North Abba Jibiya (W13)	3.75	5
Jos North Gangare (W14)	5.32	5
Jos South Dadin Kowa (W15)	7.04	5
Jos South Zaramaganda (W16)	14	5
Jos South Gyeil B (W17)	1.96	5
Jos South Bukuru (W18)	1.64	5
Jos South Abbayoir (W19)	2.22	5
Jos South Building Mat. (W20)	10.34	5
Jos South Ray field (W21)	2.3	5

Figure 3: Statistical analysis of Turbidity of the selected hand dug wells

Location	Total Hardness (mg/l)	Total Hardness WHO (mg/l)
Jos North Tafawa Balewa (W1)	47	500
Jos North Ali Kazaure (W2)	80	500
Jos North Ibrahim Katsina (W3)	570	500
Jos North Naraguta B (W4)	83	500
Jos North Jenta Adamu (W5)	98	500
Jos North Ziks Avenue (W6)	40	500
Jos North Tudun Wada (W7)	85	500
Jos North Apata (W8)	72	500
Jos North Jos Jarawa (W9)	100	500
Jos North Cole Street (W10)	32	500
Jos North Naraguta A (W11)	210	500
Jos North Dodo street (W12)	228	500
Jos North Abba Jibiya(W13)	418	500
Jos North Gangare(W14)	56	500
Jos South Dadin Kowa(W15)	18	500
Jos South Zaramaganda(W16)	80	500
Jos South Gyel B (W17)	42	500
Jos South Bukuru(W18)	40	500
Jos South Abbayoir (W19)	200	500
Jos South Building Mat. (W20)	180	500
Jos South Ray field (W21)	220	500

Figure 4: Statistical analysis of Total Hardness of the selected hand dug wells.

Location	Total Coliform (MPN/100ml)	Total Coliform NAFDAC (MPN/100ml)
Jos North Tafawa Balewa (W1)	34	10
Jos North Ali Kazaure (W2)	6	10
Jos North Ibrahim Katsina (W3)	26	10
Jos North Naraguta B (W4)	45	10
Jos North Jenta Adamu (W5)	50	10
Jos North Ziks Avenue (W6)	54	10
Jos North Tudun Wada (W7)	7	10
Jos North Apata (W8)	28	10
Jos North Jos Jarawa (W9)	39	10
Jos North Cole Street (W10)	40	10
Jos North Naraguta A (W11)	80	10
Jos North Dodo street (W12)	21	10
Jos North Abba Jibiya(W13)	45	10
Jos North Gangare(W14)	69	10
Jos South Dadin Kowa(W15)	40	10
Jos South Zaramaganda(W16)	36	10
Jos South Gyel B (W17)	23	10
Jos South Bukuru(W18)	30	10
Jos South Abbayoir (W19)	18	10
Jos South Building Mat. (W20)	35	10
Jos South Ray field (W21)	29	10

Figure 5: Statistical analysis of Total Coliforms of the selected hand dug wells.

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Conclusions and Recommendation

From the results of this assessment, the concentrations of some of the physicochemical studied were within the standard desirable limits for drinking water quality recommended by WHO and NAFDAC, except for the bacteriological parameters investigated exceeded the WHO guidelines levels.

Well water samples analyzed in the study area indicated that most of the parameters are within the approved WHO Standards for Drinking Water except wells No: 20, 4, 11, and 14 (in Mungel Jos South,) (Naraguta B, Yan shanu, Yan doya all in Jos North) have Turbidity concentration of 10.34NTU, 18.3NTU and Total Coliform of 80/100ml, 69/100ml respectively against the WHO standard guideline values of Turbidity of 5NTU and Total Coliform of 0/100ml as indicated in Figures 3, 4 and 5. Therefore, the findings revealed that some of the wells water are not in any way suitable for direct consumption as practiced in the area. However, to avoid further pollution, this study therefore recommends that the site of any well to be dug should be at least 30m away from any source of contamination and water from such wells should be treated before consumption.

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